

BLENDED LEARNING: EMERGING AS AN INNOVATIVE PRACTICE IN NEW NORMAL

Dr. Anuradha Sekhri

Abstract

After the outbreak of the coronavirus, the digital divide is adversely affecting the educational system. High-quality learning with the help of digital infrastructure can only be achieved by addressing digital gaps, which will change the landscape of school education forever. To address these challenges in online education, higher education institutions need to provide professional development for instructors, training for learners, and technical support for content development. Blended learning is a new technique of teaching that offers students a multitude of real-world skills which involve combining online with face to face teaching methods. In order to ensure continuous learning, online education is building collaboration between students, parents, and educators by strengthening connections. But due to the lack of access to a digital device and internet connection has made it harder for most of the students. There is a need to work toward this by building a solid education system to address the gaps in learning, especially for students who belong to low-income families who have suffered. In the face of the covid 19 circumstances, educational discrepancies become even more apparent. To bridge the digital divide and overcome the effects of crises in a sustained manner, In order to be inclusive, educational ecosystems must respond from a place of empathy. Blended learning brings the best of both online study and face-to-face learning - helping students stay motivated and engaged. However, to truly boost student engagement and learning outcomes, faculty must move away from computerised solutions and towards more flexible and active learning methods.

Keywords: Blended learning, Online teaching, digital divide, challenges, crises, Covid -19, Government initiatives

Introduction

Learning is not static; it is dynamic. It is being influenced by the change of time, and one of the greatest influencers are teachers.

Inaccessibility to the digital infrastructure and unpreparedness among teachers to transition to online teaching shows the gaps that need to be fixed before we decide to move towards enhanced online learning. UNICEF is scaling up blended learning approaches that combine in-person and remote instruction, critical to supporting children to recover and accelerate their understanding following the disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The way a teacher learned the lesson before is not the same way that lessons are learned now. Students nowadays think and process information fundamentally different from their predecessors. Some students might require the most intensive approach to adapting instruction – modifying instruction delivery (Iris Center, 2019).

The pandemic had underlined that when their bricks and mortar premises closed, Educational institutions were forced to rethink how to give instruction in a completely distant and mostly digital environment. As a result, we've seen a lot of technology investment. Restructuring of processes and systems to support students and parents with the challenges of home learning. To tackle this digital divide, assets will be needed on a national and regional level. In contrast, individual schools will need to reassess how their already-stretched budgets may increase support in the areas highlighted above.

Need for blended learning

The pandemic has also brought attention to educational inequity. The fact that covid-19's cloud of disruption has shattered the notion of higher education being sluggish to adjust to change and tradition-bound is a key silver lining. Blended learning not only fits into today's linked world, but it may also help students, instructors, and administrators in special ways.

- **Increased Access And Convenience**

When done well, blended courses provide enhanced accessibility and convenience without sacrificing—and in some cases, even enhancing—the qualities that many students identify with a

rewarding educational experience practical learning experience (for instance, building relationships with teachers and classmates).

- Blended courses are more effective than both face-to-face and online courses, according to educational studies. Fifty-one empirical studies comparing online education to traditional face-to-face techniques were analysed in a 2009. US Department of Education report. "Students who finished all or part of their courses online did better," says the researcher. on average, than those who took the same course... face-to-face," the study concluded (Yates et al. 2009, p. xiv).
- **They improve** the design of teaching materials. Because institutional initiatives for blended courses sometimes incorporate instructional designers or educational technologists who help the faculty in a scheduled redesign process, blended courses (like online courses) may be more consciously designed than face-to-face equivalents.
- **Guidance and triggers** have been increased. When working alone, students in a face-to-face class receive instruction from the teacher during class time and a syllabus. The course environment in a blended course provides a clear path through materials, activities, and evaluations, with specific direction at each stage.
- **It is now easier to participate in learning activities.** More students will be able to engage with resources and activities on their own time if they are made available online, resulting in more thorough learning.
- **Individualized learning opportunities** are available. The availability of digital materials helps students to self-direct certain learning activities to cover knowledge gaps because they can be accessed according to their individual needs and reviewed on demand.
- **Increased social** connection leads to increased engagement. In a face-to-face session, students may have limited

opportunity to interact with each other. and the face-to-face environment may inhibit some students from participating. Online environments that facilitate class discussions, collaboration, etc., may increase student-to-student interaction. This may, in turn, enhance their engagement with the subject matter and provide motivational benefits from the increased social interaction.

- **Decreased Costs** Blended courses can reduce costs to teachers, students, and institutions. The teacher and students can benefit from less travel time, transportation savings, and fewer parking costs. From an institutional perspective, the use of physical campus resources can be reduced.

Shulman, in 1986, believed that the usual idea of knowledge in teaching is that teachers have a set of content knowledge-specific knowledge about the subject they are teaching-and a collection of pedagogical knowledge-knowledge about how to conduct, including specific teaching methods. He calls this pedagogical content knowledge or PCK (McGraw-Hill, 2019).

Students value the use of technology in the classrooms. Moreover, teachers seemed to appreciate that technology is available to them to enhance education and make it more authentic for the students (Ruggiero & Mong, 2015).

Technology in the 21st century plays a significant role in helping the teachers in the delivery of lessons and students in learning which completes the model of PCK, and this is Technology, Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). Context is also an essential aspect of educational research and the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) framework. Still, it is often missing from TPACKresearch, or its specific meaning is unclear (Rosenberg & Koehler,2015).

The interactions between teachers, students, the learning environment, and the learning tasks are referred to as pedagogy. Teachers' pedagogical practises in the classroom have an impact on

student learning (UNESCO,2018).

The body of knowledge and information that teachers teach and that students are expected to learn in a certain subject or content area is referred to as content knowledge (The Glossary of Education Reform, 2016). Experience has a weak correlation to teaching effectiveness and, in particular, content knowledge (Irvine, 2018), which means years of preparation in college plays an important role in the building of content knowledge of the graduates. Technological Pedagogic Content Knowledge (TPACK) is a theory that was created to explain the collection of knowledge that teachers require in order to effectively teach their students and use technology (McGraw-Hill, 2019).

Supporting mixed learning with digital tools some strategies that can be utilised to help learning and teaching in a blended setting are listed below:

- 1) **Theory-practice**
- 2) **Critical thinking**
- 3) **Brainstorming**
- 4) **Cooperative Debate**
- 5) **Collaborative Writing**
- 6) **Mind mapping Learning and teaching strategies**
- 7) **Cause-effect diagrams**
- 8) **Dialogue & Discussion**
- 9) **Problem-solving**
- 10) **Reflection**
- 11) **Open education resources Learning and teaching strategies**

12) Flipped Classroom

A recent study of UNESCO (2020) highlighted that 'estimated 71 million children in India have access to the internet on devices of their family members, constituting about 14 % of the country's active internet and two-thirds of internet users in India are in the age group of 12-29 years.

A study by the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) (2020) revealed that 240 million children got severely affected amid COVID-19 across India. Similarly, a study by NCERT (2020) reflects that approximately 27% of the students do not have access to smartphones/laptops to attend classes in a virtual world. A more recent UNICEF (2020) study reflects that The COVID-19 pandemic has uncovered the deep inequalities among rich and poor, rural and urban, girls and boys, across and within countries.

During the pandemic, the Indian educational system likewise encountered an irreversible learning catastrophe. Everyone's learning experience has been influenced by school closures around the country. The pandemic has driven the industry to adopt a virtual and hybrid learning model. Information and communication technology (ICT) has helped the sector adapt to new online learning methods and survive. Various educational ideas have blossomed as a result of the crisis. Stakeholders from all throughout the country have been working hard to collaborate and innovate in a variety of ways to support kids and teachers. In light of the country's many digital education difficulties, efforts have been undertaken to maximise the potential of existing and future educational platforms so that they can be made available to everyone.

Hasan (2020), who performed a qualitative survey of 408 students during the pandemic-induced lockdown to learn about their thoughts on online teaching-learning, stated that online teaching emerged as a possible instrument to enhance students' learning remotely. To ensure that education could continue at all levels, educational institutions across India and the world shifted to an online style of instruction.

Present Scenario: Digital Divide

According to NSO data on access and use of the internet at home, the survey informs that:

- 24% in India of households had access to the internet, and 11% had a computer (including tablet) only).
- Only 46.4% had access to the internet, while 16.2% had a laptop in Punjab.
- The spatial disparities are quite pronounced in these aspects of ICT. Only 40% of Rural Households have access to a computer with the internet whereas 20% for Urban households, which is about five times that of Rural India.
- The most shocking aspect is that only 15% of Rural Households have access to internet devices, while over 42% of urban households have it. (There is a need to look at students 91% of students specifically are the access behind from urban to digital infrastructure.)

Access to the internet among currently enrolled students In Urban India, 44% had higher internet access than that of Rural India, which is only 17%. Apart from the Urban-Rural Divide in India, there exists a gap in digital literacy also. NSSO's 75% Round Station/Survey Data (2017-18) reported a significant gap in the ability to operate a computer and internet male and female population in Rural and Urban areas

Access to computer and internet

According to the latest issue of SARVEKSHANA 109 issue 2020,

- Nearly 4% of rural households and 23% of urban households possessed computer.
- Nearly 24% of the households in the country had internet

access in the survey year, 2017-18. The proportions were 15% among rural households and 42% among urban households.

- Among persons of age 15-29 years, nearly 24% in rural areas and 56% in urban areas could operate a computer.
- Nearly 35% of persons of age 15-29 years reported internet use during the 30 days before the survey date. The proportions were nearly 25% in rural areas and 58% in urban areas.
- Does the question arise how we can make online education inclusive where 91% of students do not have access to the internet and computer?
- **Availability of Smartphones:**
 - i) only 61.8% families have at least one smartphone. Among enrolled children, which was merely 36.5% in 2018.
 - ii) 75% of students receiving learning materials via WhatsApp.
- **Learning Material and Learning Activities:** As far as the availability of learning material is concerned, about 80% of children said they had textbooks for their current grade. 70.2% of children did some learning activity with the help of family members, tutors or themselves. Only 11% had access to live online classes, while 21% of students of private schools had videos or recorded classes. 60% of students studied from their textbooks, and 20% watched classes broadcast on TV.

Given that these figures haven't altered much in the last few years, the statistics makes the digital revolution in the country a difficult path ahead. It is necessary to build a more blended educational paradigm that incorporates texts and technology. While the stay-at-home requirements of the pandemic necessitated this shift, the lessons learned can be applied over the long term.

Digital Initiatives

Sharma, A. (2021) discussed initiatives to address the issues of remote learning, the MHRD has launched a slew of programmes geared toward supporting pupils, educators, and lifelong learners in their quest for knowledge. These initiatives cover broad educational requirements, ranging from learners in schools to postgraduates. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has launched a number of programmes to help students and educators deal with the challenges of remote learning. Some of the efforts effectively exploited already existing digital platforms to address the learning gaps caused by pandemics. Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA), e-Pathshala, and the National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER) were all used extensively to provide educational resources and relevant training to students and instructors across the country. ICT tools such as television and radio enabled the government reach a larger number of target people. The following are some of the country's more extensively used initiatives on a larger scale:

- 1) DIKSHA (Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing)
- 2) Manodarpan, MANODARPAN was launched by the Ministry of Education to provide psychosocial support to students for their mental health and well-being throughout the pandemic's hard periods.
- 3) TV Channels of Swayam Prabha-Swayam Prabha21 is an MHRD initiative that provides DTH channels to support and reach folks who do not have continuous internet connectivity. Study Webs of Active Learning for Young-Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM) is an acronym for complete it. Thirty-two channels are devoted on a 24x7 basis to telecast high-quality educational programs by the MHRD.
- 4) Radio Stations Across India Radio channels have been used by the federal and state governments to extend the reach and depth of educational resources to the most remote parts of the country.

5) PRAGYATA Guidelines on Digital Education

The Guidelines also stress the importance of coordinating all activities related to digital, online, and on-air education, which will benefit school-aged children across the country. DIKSHA, SWAYAM Prabha, SWAYAM MOOCS, Radio Vahini, and Shiksha Vaani are all part of the effort. Switching to digital modes of education in a country like India, which is marked by varied diversity, necessitates collaboration between multiple State/UT level organisations and National level organisations for a transition that would last beyond COVID-19.

Conclusion

Increased emphasis on blended learning could be one positive outcome from the COVID-19 crisis. Obstacles prevent blended learning models from achieving their full potential, particularly in primary and secondary education. Nevertheless, this is still a viable approach for addressing the long-standing problem of socioeconomic inequality and its consequences for educational achievement. After all, a larger emphasis on home learning necessitates educators' involvement. This should provide people from all socio-economic backgrounds with improved foundations for learning inside and outside of school. Education is a social endeavour at its core, and teachers must be empowered to use technologies to engage students in learning. Support and training for teachers in the use of remote learning technology, as well as pedagogical adjustments, are critical. With a focus on pedagogy rather than merely technology, a combination of many delivery modes is more likely to be effective. As parents and caregivers grow more involved in their children's lives, merely having content available is no longer sufficient. In a blended learning setting, parents must be involved as participants in the learning process and responsible actors.

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